

Innovative Human Resource Management Practices at Selected Private higher education Institutions in Ethiopia

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Abstract

This study aims to examine the innovative human resource management (HRM) practices employed by private higher education institutions (PHEIs) in Ethiopia. As the country's higher education sector continues to grow and diversify, PHEIs face unique challenges in attracting and retaining qualified faculty and staff. Consequently, exploring innovative HRM practices becomes essential for these institutions to create a competitive advantage, foster employee engagement and satisfaction, and ultimately enhance organizational performance. The research utilized quantitative data collection methods, to gather comprehensive insights into the innovative HRM practices employed at selected PHEIs in Ethiopia. Firstly, a review of existing literature on innovative HRM practices in the higher education sector, both within Ethiopia and globally, provides a theoretical framework for analysing the innovative practices employed by PHEIs. Additionally, primary data were collected through structured surveys involving faculty members and administrative staff at the selected private higher education institutions. The findings reveal numerous innovative HRM practices adopted by private higher education institutions in Ethiopia. These practices include flexible work arrangements, career development programs, attractive compensation and benefits packages, performance-based incentives, and organizational climate enhancement initiatives. Further the study identified there is a strong and positive correlation among and between the innovative HRM practices and organizational performance. It was also found out that 57.5% of change in performance of PHEIs in Ethiopia was resulted from innovative HRM practices. Overall, this research contributes to the understanding of innovative HRM practices within the Ethiopian higher education institutions. It offers insights and guidance to PHEIs on how to effectively manage their human resources, attract and retain talent, and create a conducive work environment that fosters creativity, innovation, and continuous improvement. Moreover, this research has practical implications for policymakers and regulatory bodies in shaping HRM practices within the Ethiopian higher education institutions and beyond.

Keywords: Innovative HRM practices, private higher education institutions, Ethiopia, organizational performance

1. INTRODUCTION

Human resource management (HRM) is a strategic and operational approach to the management of people in an organization. It is concerned with the attraction, development, motivation, and retention of employees. HRM practices can be divided into two categories: traditional and innovative. Traditional HRM practices are based on the assumption that employees are a cost to be managed. They focus on controlling and directing employees, and on ensuring that they are productive. Innovative HRM practices, on the other hand, are based on the assumption that employees are a valuable asset to be developed. They focus on empowering employees, and on creating a work environment that is conducive to innovation and creativity.

Innovative HRM practices are becoming increasingly important in higher education institutions (HEIs). HEIs are facing a number of challenges, including increasing competition, changing demographics, and the need to reduce costs. Innovative HRM practices can help HEIs to address these challenges by attracting and retaining top talent, by improving employee productivity, and by creating a more positive and productive work environment.

There is a growing body of research on innovative HRM practices in HEIs. This research suggests that innovative HRM practices can have a number of positive benefits, including: Increased employee satisfaction and engagement, improved employee productivity, reduced employee turnover, increased innovation and creativity, and improved organizational performance,

However, there are also some challenges associated with implementing innovative HRM practices in HEIs. These challenges include: The need to change the culture of the organization, the need to invest in training and development, the need to overcome resistance to change, and the need to measure the impact of innovative HRM practices.

This article attempts to find out the level of implementation of newly innovated HRM practices by selecting some Private higher education Institutions in Ethiopia and the effect of these innovative HRM practices on organizational performance of PHEIs.

2. PROBLEM STATEMENT

In recent years, there has been a growing interest in the use of innovative human resource management (HRM) practices in private higher education institutions (HEIs) in Ethiopia. This is due in part to the increasing competition for students and the need to improve the quality of education. Innovative HRM practices can help HEIs to attract and retain top talent, improve employee engagement, and reduce costs.

There are a number of innovative HRM practices that can be used in private HEIs in Ethiopia. One example is the use of performance-based pay. This involves paying employees based on their performance, rather than on their seniority or position. This can help to motivate employees to perform at their best and can also help to attract and retain top talent.

Another innovative HRM practice is the use of flexible work arrangements. This can include allowing employees to work from home, work part-time, or take extended leaves of absence. This can help to attract and retain employees who have other commitments, such as childcare or elder care.

Private HEIs in Ethiopia can also use innovative HRM practices to improve employee engagement. This can include providing employees with opportunities for development and training, giving them a voice in decision-making, and creating a positive work environment. Employee engagement can lead to improved productivity, innovation, and customer service.

Innovative HRM practices can also help private HEIs in Ethiopia to reduce costs. One example is the use of outsourcing. This involves hiring outside companies to provide certain services, such as human resources, IT, or facilities management. This can help to reduce costs and can also free up time for employees to focus on other tasks. Overall, there are a number of innovative HRM practices that can be used in private HEIs in Ethiopia. These practices can help to attract and retain top talent, improve employee engagement, and reduce costs. By using innovative HRM practices, private HEIs in Ethiopia can improve their competitiveness and provide a high-quality education to their students.

3. OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

The purpose of this study is twofold: first to understand level innovative HRM practices of implemented by PHEIs in Ethiopia; and second to measure the effect of such innovative HRM practices on organizational performance at PHEIs in Ethiopia.

4. METHODOLOGY

The study followed quantitative research approaches. This quantitative method would provide a comprehensive understanding of the innovative HRM practices at private higher education institutions in Ethiopia.

A purposive sampling technique was utilized to select a representative sample of private higher education institutions in Ethiopia. The selection criteria considered factors such as year of establishment, reputation, size, and diverse program offerings. Approximately 5 institutions were selected to participate in the study, namely Admas University College (AUC), Unity University (UU), Hope Enterprise University College (HEUC), St.Mary University (SMU) and Rift Valley University (RVU).

A structured questionnaire was developed to collect quantitative data from faculty members and administrative staffs. The questionnaire included items related to innovative HRM practices, employee satisfaction, and organizational performance. The survey data was collected using an online survey platform, ensuring anonymity and confidentiality. A likert scale which was adopted from **Sri. B. Ramachandra Rao(2020)** which was used to study innovative HRM practices in Indian bank industry was used for this study and a total of 180 questionnaires were sent to randomly selected staffs of the above five PHIEs.

5. Definition of innovation

5.1. Introduction

Innovation is a word that is derived from the Latin word **innovare**, this means “into new”. The simplest definition of innovations is doing something different. Innovation is a word that often is used in the business world and for companies this usually mean something risky, costly and time consuming (Costello & Prohaska, 2013). Innovation can also be explained as a new idea,

product, device or novelty. It is a mind-set, a way of thinking beyond the present and into the future.

An innovation is important for companies and when used well it can be a process, strategy and management technique (Kuczmarks, 2003). Innovation can at a fundamental level be the process of generating and combining ideas to make a relationship between present accomplishments and past experiences to solve a future problem. This is often associated with technological feats and it play a critical role in the world economy (Baskaran & Mehta, 2016). Innovation is big in the business world and is sustainable to create value and be strong in the competitive environment. There is a link between innovation, jobs, profit and standard of living. A common way to associate innovation with is new products, materials, new process, new services and new organizations. There is a range of definitions for innovation which often overlap and there is no clear and authoritative definition. Scientist point towards this problem and without a clear definition of innovation it will be hard to develop strategies to be innovative (Baregheh, Rowley & Sambrook, 2009).

Baregheh, Rowley & Sambrook (2009) brought a suggestion of a complete and multi stage process definitions of innovation: "Innovation is the multi-stage process whereby organizations transform ideas into new/improved products, service or processes, in order to advance, compete and differentiate themselves successfully in their marketplace"s.1334. Other definitions for innovations is that it is a process of getting new tools into a given social environment or a new tool itself. New studies shows that the definition is much broader. Innovations initiating new process or events, it also bring changes in behaviour, personnel and approach and encompass much more than simply establish an effective tool (Reiman & Dotger, 2008).

Innovation can also be described as a method and technology for new markets, new product methods and identification of new customer groups. Innovation is an activity which companies solves problems by combining knowledge (Fri, Pehrsson,& Søylen, 2013). Innovation can have different definition depending on which area you are in. The technological innovation is defined as a new market and/or a new service opportunity for a technological based invention which could lead to development, or production success (Garcia & Calantone, 2002). There has been studies that found a positive relationship between creative climate and innovation. If your workplace encourages a creative climate it can moderate effects between leadership, individual problem solving, group relations and innovation. The association between creativity and new ideas is close (Gisbert-López, Verdú-Jover & Gómez-Gras (2014).

Innovation is popular in business and is a sustainable way to add value and compete successfully. Innovation, employment, financial success, and standard of living are all related. The terms "innovation" and "new goods, materials, processes, services, and organizations" are frequently used interchangeably.

5.2. Definition of innovation

There are many definitions of innovation, many of which overlap, and there is no single, conclusive definition. Scientists have identified this issue, and it will be difficult to build creative tactics without a clear definition of what constitutes innovation (Baregheh, Rowley & Sambrook, 2009).

Baregheh, Rowley, and Sambrook (2009), proposed a comprehensive and multi-stage process definition of innovation: "Innovation is the multi-stage process by which organizations transform ideas into new/improved products, services, or processes which is useful for businesses to advance, compete, and successfully differentiate themselves in their marketplace.

A new tool itself or the act of introducing new tools into a particular social milieu is some more definitions for innovations. According to recent studies, the concept is substantially broader. Innovations don't just build a useful tool; they also start new processes or events and modify behavior, persons, and approaches (Reiman & Dotger, 2008).

Another way to define innovation is as a strategy and technology for developing new markets, new product strategies, and new customer demographics. Innovation is a process by which businesses combine their knowledge to find solutions to challenges (Fri, Pehrsson, & Silen, 2013). Depending on the industry, innovation might mean many things. A technological innovation is described as a new market or potential for a new service for a technologically based invention that may result in successful development or production (Garcia & Calantone, 2002). Studies have demonstrated a link between a creative environment and invention. A creative environment at work can have a moderating influence on leadership, individual problem-solving, group dynamics, and creativity. Innovation and creativity are closely related (Gisbert-López, Verd-Jover, & Gómez-Gras).(2014)

5.3. Concept of HRM

According to Armstrong (2014), Human resource management (HRM) is a comprehensive and coherent approach to the employment and development of people. It can be regarded as a philosophy about how people should be managed, which is underpinned by a number of theories relating to the behavior of people and organizations. It is concerned with the contribution it can make to improving organizational effectiveness through people but it is, or should be, equally concerned with the ethical dimension – how people should be treated in accordance with a set of moral values. (Armstrong, 2014).

As Keegan and Francis (2010) noted: HR work is now 'largely framed as a business issue'. The emphasis is on business alignment and strategic fit. These are important requirements but focusing on them can lead HR professionals to place correspondingly less emphasis on employee needs and motivations when developing their new and altered arrangements. A simplistic view of the business imperative permits little room for considering how HR strategy should impact on individual employees. HRM indeed aims to support the achievement of business goals but, equally, it should aim to build a relationship based on trust, openness and personal fulfilment. Human resource management can be defined as a strategic, integrated and coherent approach to the employment, development and well-being of the people working in organizations. It was defined by Boxall and Purcell (2003: 1) as 'all those activities associated with the management of employment relationships in the firm'. A later comprehensive definition was offered by Watson (2010: 919): HRM is the managerial utilisation of the efforts, knowledge, capabilities and committed behaviours which people contribute to an authoritatively co-ordinated human enterprise as part of an employment exchange (or more temporary

contractual arrangement) to carry out work tasks in a way which enables the enterprise to continue into the future.

5.4. HRM practices

Human resource management (HRM) is concerned with all aspects of how people are employed and managed in organizations. It covers the activities of strategic HRM, human capital management, knowledge management, corporate social responsibility, organization development, resourcing (workforce planning, recruitment and selection and talent management), learning and development, performance and reward management, employee relations, employee well-being and the provision of employee services.

5.5. Innovative HRM practices

As a description of people management activities in organizations the term HRM is here to stay, even if it is applied diversely or only used as a label to describe traditional personnel management practices. Emphasis is now placed on the need for HR to be strategic and businesslike and to add value, ie to generate extra value (benefit to the business) by the expenditure of effort, time and money on HRM activities. There have been plenty of new interests, concepts and developments, including innovative HRM, human capital management, engagement, talent management, competency-based HRM, e-HRM, high performance work systems, and performance and reward management. But these have not been introduced under the banner of the HRM concept as originally defined.

HRM has largely become something that organizations do rather than an aspiration or a philosophy and the term is generally in use as a way of describing the process of managing people. A convincing summary of what HRM means today, which focuses on what HRM is rather than on its philosophy, was provided by Peter Boxall, John Purcell and Patrick Wright (2007), representing the new generation of commentators.

5.5.1. Innovative recruitment & selection practices(IRS)

In today's competitive job market, organizations are looking for innovative ways to attract and retain top talent. One way to do this is to implement innovative recruitment and selection practices.

According to Adem(2018) here are some innovative recruitment and selection practices that you can use: Use AI to screen résumés. Use video interviews, Use social media to source candidates, Use gamification to engage candidates, and Use data analytics to track the effectiveness of your recruitment efforts.

There is a growing body of research on the effectiveness of innovative recruitment and selection practices. A study by Cappelli and Sherer (1991) found that innovative recruitment practices can lead to a higher number of qualified applicants. A study by Schmidt and Hunter (1998) found that innovative selection practices can lead to better hiring decisions.

However, there are also some challenges associated with implementing innovative recruitment and selection practices. One challenge is that these practices can be expensive to implement. Another challenge is that these practices can be time-consuming to implement. Despite the challenges, innovative recruitment and selection practices can be a valuable tool for organizations that are looking to attract and retain top talent.

5.5.2. Innovative Training And Development Practices(ITD)

Innovative training and development practices are those that are designed to meet the needs of the modern workforce. They are often based on new technologies and methods, and they are designed to be more engaging and effective than traditional training methods.

There are many different innovative training and development practices, but some of the most common include: Blended learning, Microlearning, Gamification, Social learning, Virtual reality (VR) training, and Augmented reality (AR) training (Adem, 2018).

Innovative training and development practices can be a valuable tool for organizations that are looking to improve employee engagement, performance, and innovation. By choosing the right practices and by providing adequate resources and support, organizations can reap the benefits of these practices.

5.5.3. Innovative Performance Appraisal Practices(IPA)

Performance appraisal is a process that is used to evaluate the performance of employees. It is a way for managers to provide feedback to employees on their work, and to identify areas where employees can improve. Performance appraisals can also be used to make decisions about promotions, raises, and terminations.

Traditional performance appraisals have been criticized for being subjective, time-consuming, and not always effective in improving organizational performance. In recent years, there has been a trend towards more innovative performance appraisal practices. These practices are designed to be more objective, efficient, and effective than traditional methods.

Some *innovative performance appraisal* practices include: 360-degree feedback, Self-assessment, Goal-setting, Peer review: 360-degree goal-setting, Self-directed goal-setting, Continuous performance management: Performance coaching (Adem, 2018).

Innovative performance appraisal practices can be more effective than traditional methods in improving organizational performance. They can provide employees with more feedback, more opportunities to develop, and more support to achieve their goals

5.5.4. Innovative Compensation Practices(ICP)

In today's competitive business environment, companies are looking for ways to attract and retain top talent. One way to do this is to offer innovative compensation practices. Innovative compensation practices are those that go beyond traditional salary and benefits packages. They can include things like flexible work arrangements, stock options, and profit sharing(Adem, 2018).

There are a number of reasons why companies are turning to innovative compensation practices. First, they can help to attract and retain top talent. In a tight labor market, companies need to offer something that sets them apart from the competition. Innovative compensation practices can do just that. Second, innovative compensation practices can help to improve employee morale and productivity. When employees feel like they are being compensated fairly and that their work is valued, they are more likely to be engaged and productive. Third, innovative compensation practices can help to reduce costs. For example, companies that offer flexible work arrangements may be able to reduce their office space costs.

5.5.5. Innovative Employee Relation Practices (IER)

Employee relations recently adopted some kind of innovation to improve firm performance, profit and competitiveness. these includes open communication, flexible work arrangements such as remote work options or flexible hours can improve work-life balance and employee satisfaction, Encouraging cross-functional collaboration and team-building activities, Establishing a formal grievance resolution process that allows employees to voice concerns and provide feedback in a safe environment, and Providing opportunities for continuous feedback and recognition for employees.

5.6. Relationship between Innovative HR practices and Performance

firm performance can be measured in different ways like result on the improvement on the financial performance like improvement in return on investment, revenue, sales, return on equity, profitability, etc. another method to see or measure performance is improvement on the non financial aspects like improvement on quality of goods or services, increased customer satisfaction, improvement on the market share, improvement on the goodwill of the firm, etc.(koang, 2012).

Zeng et al (2009) conducted a Cluster analysis to group Chinese SMEs according to their adoption of innovative human resource (HR) practices and examine how the practices are associated with HR outcomes and firm performance. The results from the hierarchical cluster analysis indicated the existence of a three-cluster solution. The first cluster had a high representation of small firms that emphasize free market selection, performance-based pay and employee participation. This group of firms had not yet implemented all of the innovative HR practices (e.g. training and development and performance evaluation). The second cluster consisted of firms that employed almost the full range of innovative HR practices. The third cluster consisted of enterprises that emphasized more traditional personal management practices. It was found that the membership of clusters is influenced by several factors, including ownership, age and size of firms. These characteristics had influenced the motivation, capacity and ability of firms in the sample to adopt high performance human resource practices. The extent to which firms had adopted innovative human resource practices was shown to be closely associated with human resource outcomes and firm performance. From the cluster analysis under this study, it was apparent that innovative HR practices among growth-oriented SMEs in China include performance-based pay, training and development, performance evaluation, encouragement of employee participation in decision making and strategic recruitment and selection. These were the practices adopted by the cluster of firms that were achieving the best HR outcomes and improved firm performance. Another key implication of this research was that domestic and collective owned enterprises (private sector firms) that wish to improve their firm performance should focus on using the HR practices that are more commonly adopted by the innovative firms (i.e. performance evaluation, training and development, provision of social benefits), though they were potentially more costly to adopt.

Racelis (2009)¹⁹ mentioned in his conference paper that high performance work practices include comprehensive employee recruitment and selection procedures, incentive compensations and performance management systems, and extensive employee involvement and training. It has been argued that these practices can improve the knowledge, skills, and abilities of a firm's current and potential employees, increase their motivation, reduce shirking, and enhance retention of quality employees while encouraging nonperformers to leave the firm (Huselid, 1995).

Barman and Singh (2010)²⁰ studied HR innovations out of recession by applying an appreciative text analysis of existing literature. In this study an attempt was also made to find out the fulcrum of innovation in the referred literatures with the support of email survey. According to these researchers, Recession is about the creative Human Resources Management. The HRM Function is asked to bring new ideas, to change the HRM processes and to develop or change the procedures. And this effort has to be cheap or it has to cut the costs of the organization. The HRM Innovation is easy in times of the business growth, but the recession is not good for big innovative HRM Initiatives. Through analytical text mining, the researchers found out the basic contents for HR innovations those are extremely relevant to corporate context and then the contents were contextualized to bring to limelight of post crisis HRM scenario. The selected contents were finalized to verify in the post crisis context; than framed as questionnaire which was used for the survey. The study confirmed that the essential points, especially in post recession period, are the ability to take a broader view of the business and to articulate the impact of HR initiatives on the bottom line.

5.7. Conceptual framework and Hypotheses

5.7.1 Conceptual framework

Based on the above literature the following conceptual framework was developed by the authors, after examining several literatures written on the specific topic.

Figure1. Conceptual Framework

5.7.2. Hypothesis

The following hypotheses were developed to test the relationship between innovative HRM and firm performance at the Private higher education Institutions in Ethiopia.

- ✓ *H1: IRS has significant effect on Organizational performance.*
- ✓ *H2: ITD has significant effect on Organizational performance.*
- ✓ *H3: IPA has significant effect on Organizational performance.*
- ✓ *H4: IEC has significant effect on Organizational performance.*
- ✓ *H5: IER has significant effect on Organizational performance.*

6. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

6.1 INTRODUCTION

This part presents the results of the analysis of the data obtained from the respondents through questionnaires and have three main section .In the first part discuss about demography related data of respondents, on the second section the researcher discuss about descriptive statistic and finally inferential analysis [correlation and regression] analysis result will be discussed .The target population for this study were academic staffs of selected private higher education. A total of 180 respondents whose educational background is diploma and above were purposively selected from the employees of the respondents. And from the distributed 180 questionnaires 149 respondents returned.

Response Rate = Number of respondents that cooperated = $(149/180) \times 100\% = 82.7\%$

6.2. DATA PROCESSING

The completed questionnaires were coded in excel and inserted into SPSS. This software program was used to analyse the data. Descriptive statistical analysis used to reduce large amount of data to summarize frequencies, means and standard deviations. Based on the descriptive statistics the collected data for each question and respondents were summarized and addition to this to analysis the data the researcher used regression and correlation analysis with the support of this software package

6.3 DEMOGRAPHICS RESPONDENT

Table 2. Demographic data Respondents

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	AUC	27	18%	18%	18%
	HEUC	33	22%	22%	40%
	RVU	15	10%	10%	50%
	SMU	36	24%	24%	74%
	UU	38	26%	26%	100%
	Total	149	100%	100	
Male and Female					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Male	97	65%	65%	65%
	Female	52	35%	35%	100%
	Total	149	100%	100	
Age [in years]					

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	18-25	9	6%	6%	6%
	26-35 Years	48	32%	32%	37%
	36-45	52	35%	35%	73%
	Above 45	40	27%	27%	100%
	Total	149	100%	100%	
Educational Level					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Diploma	11	7%	7%	7%
	BA/BSC	49	33%	33%	40%
	MA/MSc	76	51%	51%	91%
	PHD	13	9%	9%	100%
	Total	149	100%	100%	
Work Experience at PHIs					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1-2 Years	11	7%	7%	7%
	3-5 years	52	35%	35%	42%
	6-8 years	37	25%	25%	67%
	9-10 Years	26	17%	17%	85%
	Above 10 Years	23	15%	15%	100%
	Total	149	100%	100%	

Table 2, above, clearly indicate that the participants who filled and replied the questionnaire were comprising the highest from Unity university with 38(26%) followed by respondents 36(24%) from St.Mary University, then followed by Hope Enterprise University College with 33(22%) respondents. The remaining 27(18%) and 15(10%) respondents were from Alpha University College and Rift Valley University respectively.

From the total 149 respondents 72 (45 %) of them are Female respondent and 88 (55 %) of them respondent is male, this implies that male respondent greater than Female, as shown in the Table 2 above.

As indicated in Table 2 most of the respondents were categorized under MA/MSc holders are 76 (51%), while PhD holders are 13 (9%), BA/Bsc holders' are 49 (33 %) and Diploma holders are 11 (7 %) of the total valid respondents. From this we can assume that because of this level of academic position the respondents have better understanding of dimensions of innovative human resource management practices traits. Hence, the response could be reliable.

As indicated in Table 2 Work experience data in the Higher education institutions reveals that of the 149 valid respondents 11(7%) have the service year of 1to 2 years, while majority 52(35%) of the respondents had worked in the stated organizations between 3 to 5 years, those who have work experience of 6 to 8 and 9 to 10 years were 37(25%) and 26(17%) respectively. the remaining 23(15%) of the respondents had worked in the organization for more than 10 years. From this it is possible to say that the respondents were well aware about their organization cultures dimensions because most of respondent have worked in the organization within a range of three to ten years.

6.4 DESCRIPTIVE ANALYSIS

Respondents' perception towards the extent of effect of innovative human resource management practices on organizational performance. The perception of respondents on the Innovative HR practices described in view of Innovative Recruitment & Selection, innovative Training & Development, innovative employee compensation, innovative Performance Appraisal and Innovative Employee Relations with its influence on Organizational performance.

The respondents were asked about their response on effect of innovative human resource management practices and organizational performance at selected Private Higher education institutions. Table 3 below indicates the mean and standard deviation results of all the five independent and one dependent variables. These five independent variables are innovative recruitment & selection (IRS), innovative training & development (ITD), innovative employee compensation (IEC), innovative performance appraisal (IPA), and innovative employee relations (IER) while the dependent variable is organizational performance (OP).

TABLE 3: MEAN AND STANDARD DEVIATION DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS RESULT

Descriptive Statistics			
Variables	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
IRS	149	2.26	.57711
ITD	149	1.02	.66063
IPA	149	3.75	.69071
IEC	149	1.27	.65519
IER	149	1.62	.62779
OP	149	1.23	.57955
Valid N (listwise)	149		

As presented in Table 3 it is understood that the mean values of all variables were between 1.02 and 3.75. The average mean value of all variables is 1.984 and this showed as below the expected average of 2.5 out 5 point scale and implies that almost all respondents disagree on the implementation and use of innovate HRM practices at the said PHEIs. The standard deviation falls between .57711 to .69071 which shows low variation among the responses delivered by the respondents.

It clearly indicated that the level of implementation and know how the innovative HRM practices is very low at private Higher education in Ethiopia, indicating still PHEIs in Ethiopia are using the traditional HRM practices in order to attract and retain talented staffs. This is against the literatures written by many authors that they suggest implementing innovative HRM activities will be the key for being competitive in the industry.

6.5 CORRELATIONANALYSIS

Correlation test is showing the strength of the association or the relationship between the variables involved. Inter- correlations coefficients (r) were calculated by means of Pearson's product moment and Pearson's correlation was used to investigate the interrelations among the variables.

According to Cohen (1988), value ranging from 0.10 to 0.29 may indicated as low degree of correlation, value ranging from 0.30 to 0.49 may be indicating a moderate degree and value ranging from result from 0.50 to 1.00 assigned as a high degree of correlation.

TABLE 4: CORRELATIONS AMONG VARIABLES

		Correlations					
		IRS	ITD	IEC	IPA	IER	OP
Innovative Recruitment & Selection (IRS)	Pearson Correlation	1	.782**	.688**	.582**	.722**	.526**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	149	149	149	149	149	149
Innovative Training & Development (ITD)	Pearson Correlation	.782**	1	.798**	.706**	.566**	.621**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	149	149	149	149	149	149
Innovative employee compensation (IEC) (IEC)	Pearson Correlation	.688**	.798**	1	.805**	.915**	.687**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000	.000	.000
	N	149	149	149	149	149	149
Innovative Performance Appraisal (IPA)	Pearson Correlation	.582**	.706**	.805**	1	.672**	.750**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	149	149	149	149	149	149
Innovative Employee Relations (IER)	Pearson Correlation	.722**	.566**	.915**	.672**	1	.699**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000		.000
	N	149	149	149	149	149	149
Organizational Performance (OP)	Pearson Correlation	.526**	.621**	.687**	.750**	.699**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	
	N	149	149	149	149	149	149
		**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).					

As per the above table 4, correlations among variables indicate that all correlation results are positive. This implies that among variables they have positive relationship. As per the above table correlation result the relation between and among variables itself and dependent and independent is above 0.5 this implies that strong relationship between or among variables.

6.6 REGRESSION ANALYSIS

Linear regression was conducted to identify cause and effect between independent and dependent variables. And also, Regression analysis was used in order to estimate or predict the effect of independent variable on dependent variable. The significance level of 0.05 with 95% confidence interval was used. The dependent variable was Organizational performance and the independent variables include innovative Recruitment & Selection, Innovative Training & Development, innovative employee compensation, Innovative Performance Appraisal, and Innovative Employee Relations practices of HRM. The reason for using regression analysis was to assess the effect of Innovative human resource management practices on Organizational performance.

6.7 REGRESSION RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Regression analysis applied to examine and investigate the effect of innovative human resource management practices on organizational performance of organization. The coefficient of determination –R² is the measure of proportion of the variance of dependent variables, and the mean that is explained by independent or predictor variables.

TABLE 8: MODEL SUMMARY [INDEPENDENT VARIABLES AS PREDICTORS TO ORGANIZATIONAL PERFORMANCE]

TABLE 8MODEL SUMMARY

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.766 ^a	.586	.575	.37798
a. Predictors: (Constant), IRS, ITD, IEC,IPA,IER				
b. Dependent Variable: OP(Organizational performance)				

Table 8 presents the model summary which states that organizational performance as a function of innovative Recruitment & Selection, innovative Training & Development, innovative employee compensation, innovative Performance Appraisal and innovative Employee Relations and Organizational performance. Based on the above model summary R Square value indicated that the independent variables explained the dependent variable by 57.5%. This result implies innovative HR element dimensions accounted 57.5% of the variance in organizational performance.

Table 9: Coefficients Regression

Model		Coefficients						
		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	.767	.174		4.419	.000		
	Innovative Recruitment & Selection(IRS)	.036	.088	.036	.404	.687	.376	2.656
	Innovative Training & Development(ITD)	.025	.094	.084	.786	.433	.252	3.960
	Innovative employee compensation (IEC)	.034	.092	.149	.450	.149	.241	4.151
	Innovative Performance Appraisal(IPA)	.028	.094	.084	.786	.433	.252	3.960
	Innovative Employee Relations(IER)	.479	.082	.541	5.855	.000	.341	2.932

a. Dependent Variable: Organizational performance

Regression equation is stated as:

$$Y = B_0 + \beta_1 x_1 + \beta_2 x_2 + \beta_3 x_3 + \dots + \beta_k X + e_i$$

Where:

- β_0 = point of intercept
- Y = the Organizational performance of Private higher Institutions
- X_k = Innovative human resource management practices of element in Private higher Institutions
- B_k = slope of the line
- e_i = error term

As per the above table 9 the explained regression equation is stated as:

- Organizational performance(OP) = 0.767 + 0.036*IRS + 0.025*ITD + 0.034*IEC + 0.028*IPA + 0.479*IER:

Where;

- ✓ **IRS** = Innovative Recruitment & Selection;
- ✓ **ITD** = Innovative Training & Development;
- ✓ **IEC** = Innovative Employee Compensation;
- ✓ **IPA** = Innovative Performance Appraisal;
- ✓ **IER** = Innovative Employee Relations; and
- ✓ **OP** = Organizational Performance

Based on linear regression analysis, the table above reveals the Effect of each innovative human resource management practices element, i.e. the Effect of IRS, ITD, IEC IPA, and IER on

Organizational performance Private higher education Institutions of are 0.036, 0.024, 0.034 and 0.028, and 0.479 respectively. By examining this β weight of data analysis result and level of significant, the finding shows that IRS, ITD, IEC and IPA have no greater effect on OP of Private higher education Institutions on the other hand IER has greater effect on OP. And this implies that the predicted change in the dependent variable for every unit increase in that particular predictor.

This signifies with one percent increase in the value of IRS; the OP of Private higher education Institutions will increase by 0.036 percent provided that other variables remain constant the same is true for other variables for ITD, IEC and IPA. Therefore, we can conclude that IRS, ITD, IEC, and IPA have not statistically significant effect on Organizational performance of Private higher Institutions. On the other hand, the β value of IER is 0.479 where the significance level is greater than 0.05. Therefore, we can conclude that four independent variables have a no significant effect on OP but on the other hand IER have a significant effect on Organizational Performance of Private higher education Institutions because of Beta value is 0.479 as per the table 9.

Generally, the main purpose of this study is to analyze the effect of Innovative human resource management practices dimensions on Organizational performance of Private higher Institutions. From the above data analysis, Innovative human resource management practices elements which are, IRS, ITD, IEC, and IPA has no effect on organizational performance at 5 % level of significance while the dimension of IER has a significant effect on the performance of organizations.

6.8 HYPOTHESIS TESTING

The purpose of the hypothesis was to analyse whether the independent variables [IRS, ITD, IEC, IPA and IER] have a significant effect on dependent variables [Organizational performance]. And one of the most commonly used methods in statically decision making is hypothesis testing. The hypothesis test includes two hypotheses: the null hypothesis [denoted by H_0] and the alternative hypothesis [denoted by H_a]. The null hypothesis is the initial claim and is often specified using previous research or common knowledge. The alternative hypothesis is sometimes referred to as the research Hypothesis.

The decision making process for Hypothesis test can be based on the probability value (-value) for the given test that is:

- If the p-value is less than or equal to a predetermined 0.05 level of significance, then we reject the null hypothesis and claim support for the alternative hypothesis
- If the P- value is greater than 0.05 level of significance value, we fail to reject the null hypothesis and cannot claim support for the alternative hypothesis

At the 5% significance level, determine if the model is useful for predicting the response bases on this Hypothesis analysis implemented:

TABLE 10: SUMMARY OF HYPOTHESES TESTING

Type	Hypothesis	Result	Reason
H ₁	IRS has significant effect on Organizational performance	Not supported	B=0.036, P>0.05
H ₂	ITD has significant effect on Organizational performance	Not Supported	B=0.025, P>0.05
H ₃	IPA has significant effect on Organizational performance	Not Supported	B=0.028, P>0.05
H ₄	IEC has significant effect on Organizational performance	Not supported	B=0.034, P>0.05
H ₅	IER has significant effect Organizational performance	supported	B=0.474, P<0.05

7 DISCUSSION

The research was carried out in order to find the effect of innovative human resource management practices on organizational performance in Private higher education Institutions in Ethiopia. Explanatory research design was employed, and data were collected from 149 Private higher education Institutions HQ employees. In line with the objectives the following are the major finding of the study:

Employees of Private higher education Institutions about 149 were participated on the study. Among those 55% of the respondents were male and the rest were female. Majority of the respondents were Degree holders those have 3 years and above work experience. Finding of quantitative or Correlation result showed that, between dependent and independent variables have positive relationship.

From the finding the detail results on correlation results are here under:

- The correlation between IRS and **OP** is positive and significantly correlated at ($r=0.526$), ($P<0.01$), this shows that the relationship between the two variables is strong.
- The correlation between ITD and **OP** is positive and significantly correlated at (0.621), ($P<0.01$), this shows that the relationship between the two variables is strong.
- The correlation between IEC and **OP** is positive and significantly correlated at (0.687), ($P<0.01$), this shows that the relationship between the two variables is strong.
- The correlation between IPA and **OP** is positive and significantly correlated at ($r=0.750$), ($P<0.01$), this shows that the relationship between the two variables is strong.
- The correlation between IER and **OP** is positive and significantly correlated at ($r=0.699$) ($P<0.01$), this shows that the relationship between the two variables is strong.

Finding from regression analysis result:

- The independent variables selected for the model (innovative Recruitment & Selection, Innovative Training & Development, innovative employee compensation, Innovative Performance Appraisal, and Innovative Employee Relations practices of HRM), and 57.5 % of independent variable effect on **organizational performance**. But the rest variations 42.5 % are from extraneous variables. This result implies Innovative human resource management practices or element factors accounted 57.5% of the variance in

OP. So, Innovative human resource management practices elements variables explained the **OP** by 57.5 %.

The finding from regression analysis showed that there are other factors or variables that have not including in the research which affected positively on the **OP** of Private higher Institutions. In the general, the cause and effect of five variables with **OP** of PHEI is analyzed with help of **SPSS** version 24, and **IER** high value on Beta and significant /Strong effect on **OP** of Private higher Institutions

The finding of hypothesis 1 shows that the path between **IRS** and **OP** is insignificant, that is, ($B=0.036$, $P>0.05$). In other word, **IRS** has insignificant effect on **OP**. Hence, the hypothesis is not supported. With regards to hypothesis 2, the result shows that the path between **ITD** and **OP** is insignificant, that is, ($B=0.025$, $P>0.05$). Simply put, **ITD** has insignificant effect on **OP**. Hence, the hypothesis is not supported. According to the finding of hypothesis 3, the path between **IEC** and **OP** is low and insignificant, that is, ($\beta=0.034$, $P>0.05$). According to the finding of hypothesis 4, the path between **IPA** and **OP** is insignificant, that is, ($\beta=0.0$, $P>0.05$). The finding of hypothesis 5 shows that the path **IER** and **OP** is significant, that is, ($B=0.474$, $P<0.05$). In other word, **IER** has a significant positive effect on **OP**. Hence, the hypothesis is supported. This implies that **IER** has a significant positive effect on **OP**.

In General, on the above Hypothesis finding and result **IRS**, **ITD**, **IEC** and **IPA** in Private higher education Institutions happens to be the first, second, third and fourth from Innovative human resource management practices dimension that has no significant effect on **OP** respectively but as per the finding of the study **IER** has a significant effect on **OP** of Private higher Education Institutions in Ethiopia.

8 CONCLUSION OF THE STUDY

The main purpose of this study is to assess the effect of innovative human resource management practices on organizational performance and based on the research objectives, analysis of the data and finding of the study the following conclusion are drawn:

- From the demographic data of the respondents one can concluded that as statistics indicates that the majority of the respondent are diploma and above level this help the Private higher education Institutions easily understands innovative human resource management practices traits to improve Organizational performance of the case of organization and so as to make it competitive preferable on local and national.
- The correlation analysis showed that there is significant and positive relationship among and between independent variables and organizational performance. Therefore, improvement and interrelation in all independent variables can increase the organizational performance Private higher education Institutions and also increasing integration of innovative human resource management practices traits Efficiency and to overcome and keep the Private higher education Institutions distinctive competency.
- The regression and hypothesis result showed as all variable efficiency have positive and significant effect on competitive positioning of working with exception of some variable, this independent variable have positive effect but not supported by hypothesis.

According to the study, innovative human resource management practices dimensions or traits have a positive effect on employ performance this revealed that doing more on independent variables will help Private higher education Institutions to have competitive advantage. Over, all based on the analysis we can conclude innovative human resource management practices dimensions or traits has statistically significant effect on organizational performance of Private higher Institutions. Bases on this the researcher conclude that executive administration of Private higher education Institutions need to consider taking and implementing dimensions of innovative human resource management practices elements in as more effective and powerful tool in the success of competitive position.

9 RECOMMENDATION AND FUTURE RESEARCH DIRECTIONS

The researcher believes that the study could contribute a lot for Private higher education Institutions efficiency on competitive positioning. So, the main recommendations derived from this study could be describe below.

Ethiopia has great potential to work with relatively its cheap labour force. Through using this resource Private higher education Institutions can be increased competitiveness if attention is given to employee of the sector as a whole. So, Private higher education Institutions must broaden their area of strategy analysis and decision making to encompass not only the internal working units but also the whole. In modern highly competitive markets there has been reorientation of service efficiency towards collaboration between customer, strategic fast and accurate information sharing and strong relationship with customers are and important way of sustaining service positioning of the giving service this can be achieved through implementing innovative HRM practices like recruitment, selection training, compensation and other HR practices.

Employees are the building block of any organizations, so Private higher education Institutions in Ethiopia should shift from the traditional HR practices to new and innovative ways to bring and retain qualified staffs that will lead them for higher competitiveness.

Among the innovative HRM practices, private higher education intuitions in Ethiopia shall give high due regard to IER, as innovative Employee relation has a significant impact in improving the performance of such organization, as the study result shows.

DIRECTION FOR FURTHERSTUDIES

Further research need to be conducted to establish the relations between Innovative HRM on organization performance in manufacturing sector to see if there is a difference in techniques that should be applied innovative HR in manufacturing and service firms.

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11 Appendix-Questionnaire

Dear respondent, Please rate your response to the presence of the items listed Human Resource Management Practices of your College/university by using the five point scale (1)Strongly Disagree, (2) Disagree,(3)Neutral, (4) Agree,(5) Strongly Agree.

Innovative HRM practices						
A. Innovative Recruitment and selection(IRS) practices		1	2	3	4	5
1	Out sourcing the Recruitment & Selection process enables us to get the best match for our job requirements.					
2	E-recruitment is implemented by the organization including <i>Virtual or video interviews, social media platforms, & AI and Machine learning algorithms</i>					
3	Management encourages employee reference in the recruitment process.					
4	Employees of the organization are diverse in gender, race, religion, experience etc					
5	My firm/organization integrated social media platforms for sourcing and engaging with potential candidates					
6	My firm/organization uses AI & machine learning algorithms for preliminary screening					
7	Our recruitment process considers Exceptional pool of talent applicants					
8	My firm/organization incorporated virtual or video interviews as part of the selection process					
9	Organization has a mechanism in place to evaluate the recruitment process for its cost-effectiveness.					
10	Organization has a mechanism in place to evaluate the recruitment process for its flexibility.					
B. Innovative Training and development(ITD) practices						
1	Training for World Class Standards is Provided.					
2	Behavioral and Technical Trainings are provided to employees.					
3	The training schedule is planned in advance in the form of a 'training calendar' for the year.					
4	The organization provides ample scope for employee self-development.					
5	Organization conducts Executive/Manager refresher training courses.					
6	E – Learning system is implemented by the organization.					
7	The learning and development plans are reviewed periodically.					
8	We have a system in place to recognize, reward and reinforce right behaviors for employee career development.					
9	Performance evaluations are conducted regularly to avail policies for designing aspects and prospects of employee development.					
10	Employees with right potential are considered for leadership development programs.					
C. Innovative Performance Management (IPA) Practices						
1	Use of performance matrix or any other competency mapping models for my performance reviews					
2	Use of goal reviews and competency review systems					
3	Use of fair objective data of per employee results for appraisal					
4	Use of performance reviews from multiple sources e.g. superiors, students, peers etc.					
5	Permission to the staff to challenge or appeal appraisal decisions made by superiors					
6	Real-time feedback mechanisms in performance appraisals system is implemented in the our college/University					
7	Continuous performance management practices that focus on ongoing coaching and development rather than annual reviews is implemented in the our college/University					
8	Technology tools such as AI-driven performance analytics to help identify patterns and trends in employee performance is implemented in our College/University					

D. Innovative Employee compensation (IEC) practices						
1	Compensation packages of our organization are benchmarked with the industry standards.					
2	Executive compensations are categorized by flexibility, CTC, employee customs and expectations.					
3	Good performance is recognized and suitably rewarded through financial incentives.					
4	Ability and Contribution of the employee are considered while upgrading the pay-scale					
5	Compensation revisions are carried out regularly and strategically.					
6	Organization modifies the pay structures so as to align with the employee desirables.					
E. Innovative Employee Relation (IER) Practices						
1	Availability of sufficient/proper health & wellness programs					
2	Provision of flexible work arrangements such as remote work options or flexible hours					
3	Provision of Employee Assistance programs as part of employee relation package					
4	Availability of Diversity and Inclusion Programs in its employee relation task					
5	Provision of cross-functional collaboration and team-building activities can enhance employee relationships					
Organizational performance (OP)						
1	Improvement on financial performance of my college/university is exhibited due to innovative HRM practices (Such as sales, profit, ROI, etc)					
2	Improvement on non-financial performance of my college/university is exhibited due to innovative HRM practices (such as customer satisfaction, improved quality etc)					

Part-II Please suggest any other HRM practices that improves the performance of your higher institute and which are not being implemented far.
